

Coupled Galerkin-DQ Approach for the Transient Analysis of Dam-Reservoir Interaction

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Abstract : In this paper, a numerical algorithm using a coupled Galerkin-differential quadrature (DQ) method is proposed for the solution of dam-reservoir interaction problem. The governing differential equation of motion of the dam structure is discretized by the Galerkin method and the DQM is used to discretize the fluid domain. The resulting systems of ordinary differential equations are then solved by the Newmark time integration scheme. The mixed scheme combines the simplicity of the Galerkin method and high accuracy and efficiency of the DQ method. Its accuracy and efficiency are demonstrated by comparing the calculated results with those of the existing literature. It is shown that highly accurate results can be obtained using a small number of Galerkin terms and DQM sampling points. The technique presented in this investigation is general and can be used to solve various fluid-structure interaction problems.

Keywords : Galerkin method, differential quadrature method, integral quadrature method, fluid-structure interaction, Dam-reservoir system

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